

EXTRACTION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF OKRO (*ABELMOSCHUS ESCULENTUS*) TO BE USED AS AN EOR FLUID

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Abstract-This research deals with extraction and characterization of *Abelmoschus esculentus* (okro) sample to be used in enhanced oil recovery (EOR) applications. Using water based extraction method, characterization of the extracted mucilage was done by various parameters such as micromeritic studies, flow behaviour, organoleptic properties, surface tension, viscosity, ash value and swelling index. Fourier transform infra-red (FT-IR), X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analyses were carried out on okro sample. The okro mucilage used in this research was interpreted on the basis of performed XRD analysis and petrographic observations. XRD analysis was carried out using X-ray diffractometry to analyse the phase composition and identify the amorphous nature of the *Abelmoschus esculentus* (AE) mucilage. The diffraction data were collected from 2 to 70° of 2θ starting from 0.02 at 1 seconds. The result showed that extracted okro mucilage exhibited good flow properties; the surface tension of mucilage was found to be 0.0410 joule/m², water solubility index was 17.70 %, swelling capacity was 5, viscosity was 130.04 cps, total ash was 11.30 % w/w, moisture content was 4.00 %, crude fibre was 11.50 % and pH was found to be 7.5. The FT-IR analysis revealed that the okro powder is composed of organic substances such as polyphenol and carboxyl groups. The scanning electron micrographs confirm the morphology of okro sample to be more amorphous than crystalline.

Keywords :- (EOR, Okro mucilage, FT-IR, XRD, SEM).

1.0. INTRODUCTION

Natural polymers are generally obtained from plant. They are high molecular weight water soluble polymers made up of monosaccharide unit and joined by glucosidic bond, (Farooq *et al.*, 2013), and (Krishna *et al.*, 2011). Okro (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L.) is one of the most widely known and utilized

species of the family Malvaceae. Economically, okro is an important vegetable crop grown in tropical and sub-tropical regions of the world. Mostly, it is grown for its green leaves and pods as green vegetable according to Naveed *et al.*, (2009). In studies reported by Gopalan *et al.* (2007), one hundred grams (100 g) of okro contain moisture (89.6 g), minerals (0.7 g), protein (1.9 g/100 g), carbohydrates (6.4 g), fat (0.2 g), calcium (66 mg), fiber (1.2 g), calories (35 mg), potassium (103 mg), phosphorus (56 mg), magnesium (53.0 mg), and sodium (6.9 mg). Okro gum from the pods of *Hibiscus esculentus* is one of the advantageous polysaccharides that are currently being studied as a hydrophilic polymer (Zaharuddin *et al.*, 2014). Okro plant grows very fast, is grown in all soil types, and is among the most heat and drought-tolerant vegetables (Bakre and Jaiyeoba, 2009). It has been investigated as a binding agent for tablets and has also been shown to produce tablets with good hardness, friability, and drug release profiles (Okoye *et al.*, 2011). It has advantage over most commercial synthetic polymers as it is safe, chemically inert, nonirritant, biodegradable, biocompatible, and eco-friendly. Since it is widely harvested and does not require toxicology studies, it is therefore considered to be economical (Malviya *et al.*, 2011). Okro gum contains random coil polysaccharides consisting of galactose, rhamnose, and galacturonic acid. The repeating units of the gum were found to be (1-2)-rhamnose and (1-4)-galacturonic acid residues with disaccharide side chains and a degree of acetylation (DA = 58). When extracted in water, these polysaccharides can produce highly viscous solution with a

slimy appearance. Therefore, the highly viscous property of okro gum may be useful as a retarding polymer. The well-known natural polymers are aloe mucilage, guar gum, karaya gum, bhara gum, sodium alginate, locust bean gum, okro gum and linseed mucilage (Pawan *et al.*, 2001; Sujitha *et al.*, 2012). Gum as obtained from hydrocolloids of plant can be classified into two groups (i.e. anionic and non-ionic polysaccharides). Hence by modification gum can alter their physicochemical properties (Ogaji *et al.*, 2011). Mucilage is a metabolized product which is intracellularly formed without injury to the plant (Sujitha *et al.*, 2012). Gums are readily soluble in water while mucilage forms slimy mass in the presence of water. Gum and mucilage are translucent, amorphous substances which are produced by plants. They can be used as a thickener, emulsifier, sweetener, viscosity enhancer. Natural polymers have gained extensive applications and became consistently essential on daily basis (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2019). Due to their extensive application in packaging, etc. heaps of plastic wastes are generated in quite a lot of spots which have exceedingly affected the environs, permitting visual pollutions with impending dangers as well as defacing of the living cities (Ugoeze *et al.*, 2021). Natural polymers are used as an environment cleaner, renewable and also help in recycling of global carbon (Langer and Peppas, 1981; Malviya, 2010). Okro fruits are rich in vitamins, calcium, potassium, and other mineral matters. The mature okro seed is a good source of oil and protein, and has been known to have superior nutritional quality. Okro seed oil is rich in unsaturated fatty acids such as linoleic acid which is essential for human nutrition.

They are also known as ladies' finger. It is used as a binder and produces tablet formulations with good and optimum physicochemical properties. It also retards the release of drug, and it is a hydrophilic polymer. It is used as retardant, disintegrant, suspending agent, and matrix forming material. It is easily available and is quite economical. Being a natural polymer, it exhibits the property of biodegradation and mucoadhesion. Okro gum produces high viscosity mucilage at low concentrations. In continuation with the ongoing research on okro-based formulations, the major objective of the present investigation was

to prepare, formulate and develop okro gum to be used as an EOR (enhanced oil recovery) fluid.

1.1. DESCRIPTION OF OKRO

Okro (*Abelmoschus esculentus* (L.) Moench) is known in many English-speaking countries as lady's fingers (Priya *et al.*, 2014). It belongs to family malvaceae and genus *Abelmoschus*. The geographical origin of okro is disputed, with supporters of South Asian, Ethiopian and West African origins. The plant is cultivated in tropical, subtropical and warm temperate regions around the world (National Research Council, "Okra" Lost Crops of Africa, 2006). Okro can be grown on wide range of soils, but well drained fertile soils with adequate organic matter result in high yield (Akinyele and Temikotan, 2007). The crop is widely cultivated throughout the year in the tropics. Okro is a nutritious vegetable which plays important role to meet the demand of vegetable which are scanty in the market (Ahmed *et al.*, 1995). Okro plant or lady's finger was formerly included in the genus *Hibiscus*; section *Abelmoschus* in the family Malvaceae. The section *Abelmoschus* was subsequently proposed to be raised to the rank of distinct genus by Medikus 1787 (Priya *et al.*, 2014). The genus *Hibiscus* by the characteristics of the calyx, spatulate, with five short teeth, connate to the corolla and caducous after flowering. Okro originated somewhere around the Ethiopia, and was cultivated by the ancient Egyptians by the 12th century B.C.

1.2. STRUCTURE AND PHYSIOLOGY

Abelmoschus esculentus is cultivated throughout the tropical and warm temperate regions of the world for its fibrous fruits or pods containing round, white seeds. It is among the most heat and drought tolerant vegetable species in the world and will tolerate soils with heavy clay and intermittent moisture but frost can damage the pods. In cultivation, the seeds are soaked overnight prior to planting to a depth of 1-2 cm. Germination occurs between six days (soaked seeds) and three weeks. Seedlings require ample water. The seed pods rapidly become fibrous and woody, and to be edible, must be harvested within a week of the fruit having been pollinated. The fruits are harvested when

immature and eaten as a vegetable okro seed.

1.3. BIOCHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF OKRO

The composition of okro pods per 100 g edible portion is water 88.6 g, energy 144.00 kJ (36 kcal), protein 2.10 g, carbohydrate 8.20 g, fat 0.20 g, fibre 1.70 g, Ca 84.00 mg, P 90.00 mg, Fe 1.20 mg, β -carotene 185.00 μ g, riboflavin 0.08mg, thiamin 0.04 mg, niacin 0.60 mg, ascorbic acid 47.00 mg. Protein, carbohydrate and vitamin C content of okro (Lamont, 1999; Saifullah and Rabbani, 2009; Kahlon *et al.*, 2007). Consumption of young immature okro pods is important as fresh fruits, and it can be consumed in different forms (Ndunguru and Rajabu, 2004). Okro fruit is principally consumed fresh or cooked and is a major source of vitamins A, B, C, minerals, Iron and Iodine; and important vegetable source of viscous fiber but it is reportedly low in sodium saturated fat and cholesterol (Moaward *et al.*, 1984; Kendall and Jenkins, 2002). Presence of Fe, Zn, Mn and Ni also has been reported (Moyin-Jesu, 2007). Okro gives an invaluable source of vitamins, calcium, potassium and other mineral matters which are sometimes absent in the diet in developing countries. Seven days old fresh okro pods have the highest concentration of nutrients (Agbo, 2008). Carbohydrates are mainly present in the form of mucilage (Liu *et al.*, 2005; Kumar, 2009). The leaf buds and flowers are also edible (Doijode, 2001). Okro seeds have about 20 % proteins and 20 % oil (Sorapong, 2012). Okro seed oil has been found to have potential hypo-cholesterolemic effect. The possibility for an extensive cultivation of okro for edible oil as well as for cake is very high (Kumar, 2011). The oil content of some varieties of the seed can be quite high, about 40%. Oil yields from okro crops are also high. A 2009 study found okro oilsuitable for use as a biofuel (Farooq, 2010).

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) can provide a positive identification of every different kind of material (Adriane and Leandro, 2011). FT-IR analysis measures the range of wavelengths in the infrared region that are absorbed by a material. This is accomplished through the application of

infrared radiation (IR) to samples of a material. The sample's ability to absorb the infrared light's energy at various wavelengths is measured to determine the material's molecular composition and structure. Unknown materials are identified by searching the IR spectrum against a database that has a wide range of reference spectra. Materials can be quantified using the FT-IR materials characterization technique as long as a standard curve of known concentrations of the component of interest can be created. Then, the signal is decoded by applying a mathematical technique known as Fourier transformation. This computer-generated process then produces a mapping of the spectral information. The resulting graph is the FT-IR spectrum which is then searched against reference libraries for identification. The IR spectrum is a graph of infrared light absorbance by the substance on the vertical axis and the frequency (wavelength) on the horizontal axis. With the microscope attachment, samples as small as 20 microns can be analyzed as well as quantifying contaminants or additives in materials.

SEM (Scanning electron microscopy) analysis helps us to identify the bonding structure of a sample. SEM relies on the detection of high energy electrons emitted from the surface of a sample after being exposed to a highly focused beam of electrons from an electron gun. This beam of electrons is focused to a small spot on the sample surface, using the SEM objective lens (Laboratory Testing Inc. 2331 Topaz Drive, Hatfield, PA 19440). Scanning Electron Microscopy uses a focused beam of high-energy electrons to generate a variety of signals at the surface of solid specimens. In most SEM applications, data is collected over a selected area of the surface of the sample; and a two-dimensional image is generated that displays spatial variations in properties including chemical characterization, texture and orientation of materials. The SEM is also capable of performing analyses of selected point locations on the sample. This approach is especially useful in qualitatively or semi-

quantitatively determining chemical compositions, crystalline structure and crystal orientations. The SEM gives the magnified images of the size, shape, composition, crystallography, and other physical and chemical properties of a specimen. SEM was developed by von Ardenne (1938). Also, the principle of the SEM was demonstrated during 1939 by Knoll and Theile. The modern commercial SEM studies continued with extensive development in the 1950s and 1960s by Charles Oatley and his many students at the University of Cambridge. McHardy and Birnie gave historical developments along with its application to clay for SEM (Knoll and Theile, 1939).

X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD) is a technique used in materials science to determine the crystallographic structure of a material. XRD works by irradiating a material with incident x-rays and then measuring the intensities and scattering angles of the x-rays that leave the material. In summary, the crystal X-ray diffraction phenomenon results from a scattering process in which X-rays are scattered by the electrons of atoms present in the sample without changing the wavelength.

1.4. Problem statement

Low salinity polymer flooding has been conducted after low salinity environment was established by low salinity flooding (Alagic, 2010). In-situ saturation monitoring is an appropriate way to follow and measure the saturation change while flooding, as this gives vital information on how the flood front advances and informs about the possible in-situ redistribution of the fluids in the core. The concentration of the polymer influences the economy of the polymer flooding projects. Also the injectivity of polymer solution at higher concentrations is a crucial challenge for the polymer flooding design. After primary and secondary recovery energies are exhausted, about two third of original oil in place (OOIP) are left behind in the reservoir. These can only be recovered through the EOR processes.

Primary recovery can recover from zero to over 50% of the OOIP, and the secondary recovery can recover from 30 to 50% of the original oil in place. Since oil production grows at a rate greater than reserve addition, there is a need to boost the reserve,

and this lies with the application of tertiary recovery (EOR) which targets what is left (> 50 % OOIP). Most of the polymers used in the EOR applications are imported from other countries; as such it takes a lot of time. Also, the partially hydrolyzed polyacryl amide (HPAM) and biopolymer xanthan are susceptible to high temperature and their synthetic nature makes them harmful to the environment, and both are very expensive (Agi et al., 2017). Hence there is need for the use of natural polymers. In this research, extraction and characterization of okro (*Abelmoschus esculentus*) sample were conducted.

2.0. Aim and Objectives of the Study

2.01. Aim

The aim of this research was to extract and characterize the okro (*Abelmoschus esculentus*) sample to be used in EOR applications. This will be achieved through the realization of the following objectives:

2.02. Objectives

- (i) Extraction and physicochemical characterization of okro polymer.
- (ii) Spectroscopic analysis of okro through fourier transform infra-red (FT-IR) analysis.
- (iii) Mineralogical and crystallinity study of okro through X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis.
- (iv) Morphological analysis of okro through Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM).

2.1. Significance of the research

When a reservoir is flooded with polymer, the mobility ratio between the displaced fluid and the displacing fluid become favorable compared to the conventional water flooding. In the oil and gas industry, the synthetic polymer polyacrylamide in hydrolyzed form and the biopolymer xanthan are being used for this purpose. However, the polyacrylamide is susceptible to high temperature and salinity. Also, its synthetic nature makes it harmful to the environment. The biopolymer xanthan has the problem of degradation and both are very expensive. With the shortfall in crude oil price and the high cost of exploitation and drilling new wells, there is need to look inward and think out of

the box in formulating new improved polymers that can combat these problems. Natural polymers from agricultural and forest produce are abundant in nature, cheap and environmentally friendly. These agricultural and forest produce contain starch and cellulose which are known to have rigid and long polysaccharide chains that can withstand the harsh reservoir conditions (Augustine *et al.*, 2018). With the application of EOR using natural polymers additional oil will be recovered from the oil fields. Also, this research work will result in economic boom to the oil and gas industries, job creation, and increase in the nation's GDP (Gross Domestic Product).

3.0. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Okro sample collection and preparation

Okro (*Abelmoschus esculentus*) was obtained from local market of Muda Lawal in Bauchi, Bauchi State, Nigeria. Collected Okro was carefully washed and dried under shade for 24 h, and further dried in an oven at 40 °C until constant weight was obtained. Okro size was pulverized through grinder. Powdered fruit was then passed through sieve no. #22 and stored in air tight glass container for further use. They were further dissolved with fresh water at 60 °C and stirred vigorously for proper dissolution. However, the dissolution was incomplete as there were undissolved particles still floating in the solution. These particles were carefully sieved out to obtain a fairly clear solution.

3.1.2. Chemicals/reagents

Analytical grades of the following reagents were used in the course of this research. They include: sulphuric acid, petroleum

ether, molish's reagent, sodium hydroxide, distilled water, pH indicator (methyl red and methyl blue) and hydrochloric acid

3.1.3. Apparatus and equipment

The following apparatus and equipment were used during the course of this study: Laboratory oven, pH meter, viscometer, sieve no. #22, desiccator, soxhlet apparatus, round bottom flask, filter paper, kjeidahl flask, petri dish and volumetric flask.

3.2. Methods

3.2.1. Extraction Procedure for *Abelmoschus esculentus*

The extraction of mucilage was carried out according to the procedure by (Malviya, 2011; Gemede *et al.*, 2016) with little modification. 100 g of the powdered okro was dissolved in 300 ml of distilled water. This was heated and stirred continuously at 60°C for approximately 4h. The concentrated solution was carefully sieved and cooled at 6 °C.

3.3. Physicochemical characterization of okro mucilage:

3.3.1. pH

The pH was determined by the method as described by AOAC (2005). Two grams (2.0 g) of okra seed flour each was poured into three beakers containing 20 ml of distilled water and allowed to stand for a while and an electric digital pH meter was used to determine the pH of the samples (Lala, 1981). The pH meter was dipped into the sample and the reading was taken after about 4 min when it was stable. The pH of the okro mucilage was determined in triplicate for statistical analysis to be more valid, and was found to be 7.5 as shown in the table 1 below:

TABLE 1: pH

Sample	pH		
Trial	1	2	3
Okro	7.5	7.5	7.5

3.3.3. Bulk Density, g/cm³

Accurately weighed amount of the dried okro sample (10 g) was taken and kept in a bulk density apparatus. The volume was noted. Hence, the bulk density (Malviya *et al.*, 2010) was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Bulk density} = \frac{\text{Weight of powdered sample}}{\text{Bulk volume}} \dots \dots (1)$$

3.3.4. Viscosity

The viscosity of *Abelmoschus esculentus* was determined by using Oswald’s viscometer. The viscosity was then calculated using the following equation (Lala, 1981; Farooq *et al.*, 2013).

$$S = W \times \frac{t_s \rho_s}{t_w \rho_w} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

where, S=Viscosity of solution, W=Viscosity of water, t=time, and ρ=Density

3.3.5. Surface tension

It was determined by drop count method, using a stalagmometer according to the procedure of (More and Hajare, 2010 ; Malviya *et al.*, 2010). Surface tension was calculated using the following equation (Farooq *et al.*, 2013):

$$\sigma_2 = \frac{\rho_2 n_1}{\rho_1 n_2} \sigma_1 \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

where, σ_2 = Surface tension of okro mucilage, σ_1 = Surface tension of distilled water

ρ = Density of liquid, and n =number of drops of liquid

3.3.6. Test for Carbohydrate

0.5 ml of aqueous extract of okro mucilage was mixed with 2 drops of Molish’s reagent followed by addition of 5 ml of sulphuric acid (see table 2). The violet color ring appeared at junction, showing presence of carbohydrates (John, 1931; Kim DY and Kim H, 2022).

TABLE 2: Test for Carbohydrate

Test	Observation	Inference
Okro sample solution + Molish’s reagent + sulphuric acid.	violet color ring was observed at junction	Carbohydrate was confirmed.

3.4. Proximate analysis

Proximate analysis of moisture content, crude protein, ash content, and lipid content of the dried okro powdered samples were determined according to AOAC (2005); Ezekiel *et al.*, (2020). The percentage of total carbohydrate content of *Abelmoschus esculentus* seed flour sample was calculated by subtracting the percentage of moisture, ash, protein, and fats obtained from 100.

3.4.1. Moisture content

This was carried out after drying the okro sample. The dried sample was taken and 1 g was weighed. After the weight was recorded, the sample was dried in a hot air oven at a temperature of 105 °C. The weight was recorded at regular time intervals. This continued until a constant weight was observed. The percentage of moisture content (Lala, 1981) was calculated using the equation.

$$\text{Moisture content} = \frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100 \dots (4)$$

The okro sample was stored in an airtight container after its pulverization and sieving before constitution to be used as an EOR fluid.

3.4.2. Ash content

Determination of ash content (Pharmacological Assays of Plant-Based Natural Products, 2016). The five grams (5 g) of the powdered sample was weighed into a pre-weighed labeled crucible and placed in the muffle furnace at a temperature of 450 °C for 20 min. The furnace was allowed to cool before removing the crucible with its content. The crucible was later cooled in a desiccator and reweighed to get the ash content. The result was calculated as follows (Parimelazhagan, 2016; Kipo *et al.*, 2023).

$$\text{Total Ash value} = \frac{\text{weight of the ash}}{\text{weight of the gum}} \times 100 \dots (5)$$

3.4.3. Lipid content

Determination of lipid content (AOAC, 2005). 5.0 g of the powdered sample was put into the soxhlet extractor thimble wrapped with a filter paper and plugged tightly with cotton wool; 150 ml of petroleum ether (bpt 60-80 °C) was poured into 300 ml round bottom flask containing anti-bombings and the soxhlet extractor assembly. The sample was extracted for 4 h until the extract become colourless. The extract was poured into a dried pre-weighed beaker and the thimble rinsed with a little quantity of petroleum ether back into the beaker. The beaker was heated on a steam bath to drive off the solvent. The extracted fat left in the beaker was dried in a desiccator and weighed.

3.4.4. Crude fibre

Determination of crude fibre content: The 5.0 g of powdered sample was put in a pre-weighed beaker; 50 ml of 1.25% H₂SO₄ solution was added and made up to 200 ml with distilled water and stirred. The mixture was heated with continuous stirring for thirty (30) minutes and allowed to cool and settle. Distilled water was added and allowed to settle, and then decanted. Decantation was repeated for six times consecutively to make the mixture acid free; 50 ml of 1.25% NaOH was added to 200 ml of distilled water in a beaker and heated for thirty (30) minutes with continuous stirring. It was cooled and allowed to settle. Distilled water was added and decanted for six times consecutively. The mixture was filtered with filter paper and kept for forty-five (45) minutes for water to drain completely and the weight taken.

3.4.5 Protein content

Determination of crude protein content (Modified Kjeldahl method): The analysis was carried out in three (3) stages, these were;

- The digestion stage.
- The distillation stage.
- The titration stage.

Digestion stage: 5 g of the powdered sample was weighed out into a 250 ml kjeldahl flask. 2 g each of the kjeldahl catalysts (Copper Sulphate and Sodium Sulphate) were weighed into the kjeldahl flasks. Anti-bumping granule was added and 30 ml of concentrated Sulphuric acid was also added to the flask. The digestion flask was then placed on the heating mantle for an hour before being transferred to electric stove. The digestion process proceeds with occasional swirling until a clear solution was obtained. The clear solution was transferred into a 100 ml standard flask and made up to the mark with distilled water.

Distillation stage: The 10 ml of the digest was measured into the micro distillation apparatus. 12.5 ml of 1.25 % NaOH was also added to the flask. A condenser was connected from the distillation apparatus to a volumetric flask containing 10 ml of 5 % boric acid and 2 drops of double indicator (methyl red and methyl blue). The distillate was collected in a flask and then titrated with 0.1 ml standard hydrochloric acid until a pale pink colour end point was obtained (see table 3).

$$N \left(\frac{g}{kg} \right) = \frac{TD \times Mol.Wt. \times n}{Weight \text{ of sample in grams}} \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

where: TD =

Titre difference between Blank titer and sample titer

n = Normality of the acid used

N = Nitrogen ionic ($\frac{g}{kg}$)

TABLE 3: Protein content

Titration	1	2	3	Blank
Final Burette Reading (<i>cm</i> ³)	7.30	14.6	21.8	15.20
Initial Burette Reading (<i>cm</i> ³)	0.00	7.30	14.60	0.00
Vol. of acid used (<i>cm</i> ³)	7.30	7.30	7.20	15.20

3.5. Swelling capacity

Swelling capacity (CP) of the powdered okro was determined using the method of (Ohwoavworhwa and Adelakun, 2005; Kornblum and Stoopak, 1973) with little modification as follows: 1.0 g sample was placed in each of four 15 ml plastic centrifuge tubes to which 10 ml of distilled water was added and then stoppered. The contents were mixed on a vortex mixer for 2 min. The mixture was allowed to stand for 10 min and then centrifuged at 1000 rpm for 10 min on a bench centrifuge. The supernatant was carefully decanted, the stopper replaced and the sediment weighed. The final volume of the mixture was 10.5 ml. Swelling capacity was calculated as follows;

$$S = (V_2 - V_1)/V_1 \times 100 \dots \dots (7)$$

where S is the % swelling capacity, V2 is the volume of the hydrated or swollen material and V1 is the tapped volume of the material prior to hydration.

3.6. Water solubility index (%)

Water Solubility Index (WSI)

2 g of powdered okro sample was weighed into a 50 mL centrifuge tube and 30 mL of distilled water was added to it at 30 °C, and then stirred intermittently for 30 min. The solution was centrifuged for 10 min. The supernatant and pellet were carefully poured into a Petri dish, and allowed to dry overnight (Monique, *et al.*, 2016).

Calculation:

$$\text{Water solubility index} = \frac{\text{weight of dried supernatant}}{\text{weight of powdered sample}} \times 100 \dots (8)$$

3.7. Fourier Transform Infra-red (FT-IR) Analysis

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis measures the infrared region of the electromagnetic radiation spectrum, which has a longer wavelength and a lower frequency than visible light. This spectrum is measurable in a sample when submitted to infrared radiation (IR). The basic theory at work is that the bonds between different elements absorb light at different frequencies. FT-IR analysis was used to identify the presence of organic and inorganic

compounds in the okro sample. Depending on the infrared absorption frequency range, 400-4000 cm^{-1} , the specific molecular groups prevailing in the sample were determined through spectrum data in the automated software of spectroscopy.

3.8. X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) Analysis

X-Ray Diffraction test was done to find out the orientation of the polymeric chain such as crystalline, microcrystalline or amorphous present in the okro sample. This X-ray diffraction measurement was performed using an X-ray diffractometer. A copper K- α X-ray source with 40 kV voltage and 40 mA power was used to record the diffraction patterns. The intensity as a function of the scattering angle is evaluated by the MS Excel spreadsheet tool after getting the diffraction patterns. The wavelength of the electron beam was Lambda, $\lambda = 1.54063$. The measures the infrared region of the electromagnetic radiation spectrum, which has a longer wavelength and a lower frequency than visible light. This spectrum is measurable in a sample when submitted to infrared radiation (IR). The basic theory at work is that the bonds between different elements absorb light at different frequencies. FT-IR analysis was used to identify the presence of organic and inorganic compounds in the okro sample. Depending on the infrared absorption frequency range, 400-4000 cm^{-1} , the specific molecular groups prevailing in the sample were determined through spectrum data in the automated software of spectroscopy.

3.9. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) analysis for okro powdered sample

The scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was performed to examine the physical structure change of okro sample using SEM model Phenom ProX, by phenomWorld Eindhoven, The Netherlands. Sample was placed on double adhesive which was on a sample stub, was coated sputter coater by quorum technologies model Q150R, with 5nm of gold. Thereafter it was taken to the chamber of SEM machine where it was viewed

via NaVCaM for focusing. Thereafter it was taken to the chamber of SEM machine where it was viewed via NaVCaM for focusing and little adjustment, and SEM was operated at an accelerating voltage of 15 kV, and the image was recorded. Afterward the morphologies of different magnification were stored in a USB stick.

4.0. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Physicochemical characterization of okro mucilage

The physicochemical characterization of okra mucilage has been calculated as shown in section 3.3. The summary of the results obtained in micromeritic characterization of the mucilage are shown in Table 4.

The results in the present study confirm the results reported from previous study by Shayeri and Rana (2019) where they found that okro was light brown, odorless and tasteless. The pH of okro mucilage was found to be 7.5. This is in line with other research studies (Dhobale *et al.*, 2019; Elkhalfifa *et al.*, 2021). Presence of carbohydrate in the okro mucilage was confirmed; and the value of bulk density which was found to be 0.690 g/cm³ are in agreement with recently published results (Falguni and Atul, 2021).

Similar results in which the viscosity and surface tension of okro mucilage are 130.04 cps and 0.0410 joules/m² are confirmed in other studies by Farooq *et al.*, (2013) and Shayeri and Rana, (2019). The moisture content of okro mucilage studied (4.00 %) falls within the acceptable range of 0 %–13 % (James, 1995; Ofori *et al.*, 2020). The total ash, lipid and protein content in the present findings have values 11.30 %, 1.20 % and 22.14 respectively, are in line with the study of Gemede *et al.*, (2016). The water solubility index (17.70 %) obtained in the present study is contrary to the result reported from previous study by Ofori *et al.*, (2020), where they obtained 14.10 % using Agbagoma okro specie. These variations in the water solubility index of okro mucilage could

be due to several factors, such as the cultivation region of pods, breed of okro, and maturation state of okra pods (Lengsfeld *et al.*, 2004).

The crude fibre content (11.50 %) obtained in the present study falls within the range of 10.15 to 11.63 g, as reported by Adetuyi *et al.*, (2011) and Gemede *et al.*, (2016). The swelling index of okro mucilage at pH 7.5 was 5.0, which is again similar to what was reported by Elkhalfifa *et al.*, (2021).

4.2. Fourier Transform Infra-red (FT-IR) analysis for okro sample

Okro powder is composed of organic substances formed by functional groups such as polyphenol and carboxyl that serve as active sites for wettability alterations. The identification of functional groups present in okro powder was performed by infrared spectroscopy. Fig. 1 shows FT-IR spectrum of okra powder in the resolution range of 4000–400 cm⁻¹. In figure 1, the larger band in the region of 3600–3100 cm⁻¹ with a sharp peak centered at 3283.8 cm⁻¹ is characteristic O-H stretching vibration and hydrogen bond of the hydroxyl groups. Absorption peaks at 2926.0 and 2117.1 cm⁻¹ correspond to C-H stretching vibration from methyl and methylene group in cellulose and hemicellulose components; while at 1733.2 cm⁻¹ refers to the carbonyl C=O stretching vibration of unconjugated ketone, carboxylic acid and ester in lignin and hemicelluloses. The shoulder at 1606.5 cm⁻¹ may be due to the presence of water in the fibres. A little peak at 1401.5 cm⁻¹ is associated to the angular deformation on the O-H bonding plane. The two peaks observed at 1364.2 cm⁻¹ and 1315.8 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum indicate the bending vibration of C-O and C-H groups of the aromatic ring in polysaccharides. Furthermore, the absorption peaks around 1237.5 and 1013.8 cm⁻¹ belong to polysaccharide in cellulose and indicate the presence of C-O bonds associated with the presence of functional groups such as alcohol, ether and ester. This result is similar to what has been reported by De Rosa *et al.*, (2010) and De Rosa *et al.*, (2011).

TABLE 4: CHARACTERIZATION OF THE OKRO GUM

S/NO.	Parameters	Report
1	Color	Light brown
2	Odor	Odorless
3	Taste	Tasteless
4	pH	7.5
5	Carbohydrate	Present
6	Bulk density	0.690 g/cm ³
7	Viscosity	130.04 cps
8	Surface Tension	0.0410 joules/m ²
9	Moisture content	4.00 %
10	Total Ash	11.30 %
11	Lipid content	1.20 %
12	Protein content	22.14
13	Crude Fibre	11.50 %
14	Swelling Power	5
15	Water Solubility Index	17.70 %

Table 5: Main mineralogical composition of okro sample

Mineral	Chemical formula	Concentration (weight %)
Periclase	MgO	19
sylvine	KCl	8
Brushite	CaH ₂ PO ₄ .2H ₂ O	25
Lime	CaO	4
Hopeite	Zn ₃ (PO ₄) ₂ .4H ₂ O	20
Garnet	3(Ca,Fe,Mg)O.(Al,Fe) ₂ (SiO ₄) ₃	1
Tridymite	SiO ₂	10.7
Oxammite	C ₂ H ₅ N ₂ O ₄ .H ₂ O	1
Halite	NaCl	13.1

Figure 1: FT-IR spectrum of okro.

Figure 2: Piechart showing the mineralogical composition of okro sample.

Figure 3: SEM images of the 179-895 μm okro intervals in powdered sample.

Figure 4: The XRD pattern for okro sample.

4.3. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) analysis for okro

The SEM image shows the uniform distribution of the pores which appeared to be heterogeneous in nature, and gives a well-defined appearance of the mesh (figures. 3 A,

B, C, and D). Morphological analysis revealed that all particles had a glass structure and rough surfaces. Figure 3 A shows the 300 time magnified structure of the particle while figure 3 B shows 1000 time magnified structure. Figure 3 C and figure 3 D show 1500 and 500 time magnified structure of

the okro particle respectively. This result agrees with the result of Sury and Krishan (2022). XRD Analysis for okro sample X-Ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was carried out using X-ray diffractometry to identify the amorphous nature of okro sample. The diffraction data for the okro sample were collected from 2 to 700 of 2θ starting from 0.02 at 1 seconds. The analysis was carried out to analyze the phase composition of the okro sample as shown in figs. 2 and 4 and table 5.

5.0. CONCLUSION

Okro is a natural polymer obtained from the pods of okro plant. It has been extracted and used in the mucilaginous form. The physicochemical characterization of okro polymer was performed using standard methods. The result showed that extracted okro mucilage exhibited good flow properties; the surface tension of the mucilage was found to be 0.0410 joule/m², total ash was 11.30 % w/w, bulk density was 0.690 g/cm³, moisture content was 4.00 %, lipid content was 1.20 %, crude fibre was 11.50 %, swelling power was 5, water solubility index was 17.70 % and the presence of carbohydrate was confirmed. The pH was found to be 7.5. Okro mucilage has acceptable pH and organoleptic properties, so can be easily used to formulate natural polymer. Extracted mucilage was soluble in warm water while insoluble in organic solvents. The results obtained from this study showed that it can be safely used as an EOR agent without causing any

adverse effect to the reservoir and its fluids.

The spectroscopic analyses of okro were performed through fourier transform infra-red (FT-IR) analysis. The FT-IR analysis revealed that okro powder is composed of organic substances formed by functional groups such as polyphenol and carboxyl that serves as active sites for wettability alterations.

The mineralogical and crystallinity study of okro sample was carried out through X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis. The x-ray diffraction analysis confirmed the nature of okro mucilage to be more amorphous than crystalline. The obtained pattern on okro sample shows a mostly amorphous material including sylvine, brucite, lime, hopeite garnet, tridymite, oxammite, and halite with one crystalline phase which is the periclase.

The morphological analysis of okro sample was done using the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) at high magnification. The scanning electron micrographs reveal the particles with rough surfaces.

The results obtained from this study established the fundamental characteristics of okro mucilage. It has good physicochemical properties i.e., hardness, friability, disintegration time, and due to its swelling ability, and therefore can be used successfully for EOR applications in the oil industry under reservoir conditions. In addition, okro is readily available, biodegradable, biocompatible, and also has swelling properties.

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